

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19164836

Effects Of Experiential Teaching Strategy On Senior Secondary School Students' Interest, Achievement And Retention In Physics In Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Effects of Experiential Teaching Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students' Interest, Achievement and Retention in Physics in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Six (6) objectives and six (6) research questions guided the study while six (6) null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the pretest, posttest, control group quasi-experimental research design. The target population of this study was 12036 which was the population of SSII Physics students in the study area. Data were collected from a sample size of 160 students comprising 106 boys and 54 girls drawn from 2 schools within 2 Area Councils out of 6 Area Councils in the FCT selected using purposive sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection were Physics Interest Scale Questionnaire (PISQ), Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and the Physics Retention Test (PRT). They were validated by experts, and reliability values of 0.80 and 0.90 using Split half and Pearson product moment correlation coefficients respectively were obtained. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions and the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Major findings of the study revealed that students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy had significantly higher mean interest, achievement and retention scores than those taught using conventional teaching strategy. There was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students who were taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy. However, there were no differences statistically between the mean interest and retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Physics teachers should accept experiential teaching strategy as an effective strategy and start to use it. Experiential teaching strategy is not gender sensitive therefore both male and female students should be involved in it, and Physics teachers should be encouraged to use it to improve and bridge the gap between male and female students' academic achievement in Physics.

Keywords: Experiential teaching strategy; interest in Physics; achievement in Physics; knowledge retention in Physics; conventional teaching strategy; gender.

INTRODUCTION

Physics as one of the natural sciences has been recognized as the foundation of advancement in technology and development (Kaku, 2015). It is on this context that Physics Teachers are increasingly seeking ways of enhancing the quality of teaching and learning of Physics in our secondary schools. Physics is the branch of science that deals with the structure of matter and how the fundamental constituents of the universe interact. It studies objects ranging from the very small using quantum mechanics to the entire universe using general relativity (Mark, 2016). Physics is also seen as a discipline that is abstract but despite this abstract nature, its teaching is to bring about scientific thinking in Physics students, a mindset that requires students to be tested through observation and experimentation (Wilbert, 2016). Therefore, it is important to note that Physics as a subject is one of the core science subjects that is required for further learning and teaching for other science-related professional courses such as Engineering, Medicine and life sciences e.g. Botany, Microbiology, Biochemistry, Zoology, etc.

Despite the huge national importance placed on Physics learning at the senior secondary school level, indices from an examination body, such as the National Examination Council (NECO) have shown a consistent trend of poor achievement of students in Physics examinations in Nigeria. The aforementioned statement is attested to in the result of students in the National Examination Council (NECO) Secondary School Certificate Examination June/July, 2015 to 2024.

This situation of fluctuation in achievement of students in Physics has affected the educational pursuits and aborted the ambition of many candidates that aspired to study professional courses in tertiary institutions. Omeodu and Utuh (2018) argued that the unclear relationship between the Physics concept, laws and equations is a challenge in the teaching of some of Physics topics and more so leads to students' low interest, achievement knowledge retention towards Physics learning. It is clear that Physics Educators are questioning the teaching and learning strategies that will enable Physics students to gain proper understanding and application of Physics concepts and principles. These teaching strategies according to Ahmad (2018) will aid Physics students to have positive interest, achievement and knowledge retention in Physics.

Usaini and Abubakar (2018) observed that for quite some time several teaching strategies such as the conventional strategies have been employed in the teaching of Physics but the students' achievement in Physics examinations is yet to show a consistency of improvement. Ameh and Dantani (2019) criticized the use of conventional discussion teaching strategy used by Physics teachers in teaching because according to them, it is only the dedicated and intelligent students that benefit from it. They equally stress that the discussion teaching strategy promotes rote learning.

Gender is a moderating variable in this study. The influence of gender on the dependent variables of this study is explored. There might have been conflicting reports in respect to gender and performance in science. Umoru (2019) in a study noted that gender is not a significant factor in students' achievement; since there is an improvement in both male and female achievement scores. Solomon (2019) in another study opined that boys perform better than girls in achievement. Boys or girls may retain more or less Physics concepts and principles when taught in a science classroom. Tyler cited in Okeke (2019) reported that girls retain more than boys in the sciences. They may also retain equally or not been influenced at all in terms of gender. Gender gap may be reduced in Physics students' interest, achievement and retention; if the students offering Physics are exposed to optimum learning opportunity. This is in line with the findings of Ozden and Gultekin (2019) and Saleh and Subramaniam (2019) who concluded that optimum learning opportunities for all students can close-up the gap between male and female performance in Physics. This denotes that the optimum learning opportunity requires shift from conventional strategy of teaching to a suitable pedagogical strategy. However, in an attempt to shift from the traditional or conventional strategy of teaching and to identify a suitable pedagogical strategy for teaching Physics so as to enhance students' interest, achievement and knowledge retention, many conceptual patterns and strategies such as guided inquiry, cooperative strategy, problem solving, activity based strategy among others have been advocated for, yet they seem not sufficient as noted by Aina and Keith (2019).

From the foregoing, it is important to note that teachers and instructors of Physics would need to develop a well-articulated rationale for teaching and learning experiences that will help in shaping their choice of

teaching strategy. The situation therefore calls for the use of other teaching or learning strategies which have been found effective in some other subjects' areas and countries. Precisely in Physics, not much work has been done to ascertain the efficacy of experiential strategy in the teaching of Physics. It is of the best interest to note that experiential teaching strategy has the potential to bridge the gap between module and practical laboratory sessions in teaching and learning Physics. Researchers such as Bada and Akinbobola (2019), and Ilhami (2020) have researched into the effectiveness of experiential teaching strategy and found it useful.

Experiential teaching strategy accentuates the part of hands-on, individual involvement in building information. It is a strategy that is very valuable for competency improvement since it furnishes student with a chance to hone their abilities and think about the experience. It is on the above basis that this study was set out to examine the effects of experiential teaching strategy on senior secondary school students' interest, achievement and retention in Physics in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The high rates of failure recorded by Students in public schools in Nigeria have been a major concern to researchers. Consequently, the low achievement in Physics in external examinations such as Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE) conducted by National Examinations Council (NECO) had been traced to the use of conventional teaching strategy that does not put into consideration the students' activity in teaching and learning processes. Physics being a core science subject at the senior secondary school level of education is expected to serve as a base for scientific and technological knowledge that will enable the students to fit into the scientifically and technologically progressive society. A good number of students that offer science and science-related courses in higher institutions are expected to pass Physics at credit level. Despite this expectation, low achievement in Physics by students appear to have persisted which is often blamed on poor teaching strategies adopted.

Poor strategy of teaching invariably translates to students' lack of interest, poor academic achievement, inability to retain knowledge and to put into practice what is learnt in reality has become a hydra-headed problem. In most cases what is taught in classroom cannot be transferred to real life situation by students. Anyagh (2018) revealed that no matter how suitable the educational objectives and content might be the curriculum process will remain defective if viable instructional strategies are not adopted in the task of teaching.

The nation's quest for science and technological advancement will become a mirage, if effective modality is not put in place to incorporate innovative strategies that promote active learning and considering the importance of Physics in all round development, there is need to make sure that Physics is properly taught, most especially the difficult concepts such as mechanics, heat, waves, light waves and sound waves using innovative strategies such as experiential teaching strategy. This study therefore, examined the effects of experiential teaching strategy on senior secondary school students' interest, achievement and retention in Physics in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the effects of experiential teaching strategies on Senior Secondary School students' interest, achievement and retention in physics in the Federal Capital territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The study was guided by 6 objectives, which were to:

1. determine the difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy;
2. find out the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy;
3. determine the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy;

4. find out the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy;
5. investigate the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy; and
6. find out the difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?
2. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?
3. What is the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?
4. What is the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?
5. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?
6. What is the difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses were stated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.
- Ho₃:** There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.
- Ho₄:** There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.
- Ho₅:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.
- Ho₆:** There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework explained how experiential teaching strategy influences senior secondary school students' interest, achievement, and retention in Physics in the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja). Experiential teaching strategy, including hands-on activities, simulations, fieldwork, and group projects, served as the independent variable and are expected to improve learning outcomes by actively engaging students in meaningful learning experiences. The framework highlights the experiential learning process (active engagement, conceptual understanding, skill development, and reflective thinking) as the pathway through which instructional strategies affect students' learning. These processes facilitate deeper understanding of Physics concepts, enhance motivation, and promote long-term retention. Students' interest, achievement, and retention constitute the dependent variables, representing affective, cognitive, and memory-related outcomes of learning Physics. The framework further identifies gender as the only moderating variable, suggesting that the effectiveness of experiential teaching strategies may differ between male and female students.

Empirical Review

Empirical evidence across diverse educational contexts consistently demonstrates the effectiveness of experiential and active-engagement teaching strategies in improving students' learning outcomes, particularly achievement, interest, and retention in science-related subjects. Collectively, the reviewed studies provide strong theoretical and empirical grounding for examining experiential teaching strategy in Physics, with increasing attention to moderating variables such as gender.

Early evidence from outside Africa is provided by Zulkifli and Nurul (2017), whose quasi-experimental study in Malaysia established that students exposed to experiential learning in computer studies significantly outperformed peers taught using traditional methods. The use of pretest–posttest control group comparisons and inferential statistics strengthened the internal validity of their findings, confirming experiential learning as a potent instructional strategy for enhancing academic achievement in technology-oriented subjects.

Within the Nigerian context, several studies reinforce these findings. Ayomikun and Ogbonna (2019) demonstrated that experiential teaching strategy significantly improved secondary school students' achievement in Physics in Lagos State, highlighting its relevance to abstract scientific concepts. Similarly, Bada and Akinbobola (2020) and Bada and Jita (2021), both conducted in Ondo State, reported that experiential teaching strategies led to significantly higher retention of Physics concepts compared to conventional approaches. Notably, these studies also examined learner-related variables such as self-efficacy and found that experiential strategies enhanced retention irrespective of students' confidence levels, suggesting the robustness of the approach across individual differences.

Beyond Physics, related science disciplines further validate the effectiveness of experiential strategies. Oyeyemi, Olorundare, and Bolaji (2021) found improved retention in Biology among students taught using experiential strategies in Kwara State, while Musa, Achor, and Ellah (2021) reported superior achievement and retention outcomes in Basic Science when simulation-based strategies were employed in Kogi State. These findings collectively suggest that experiential approaches transcend subject boundaries within science education.

Studies outside Nigeria provide complementary insights. Ngaine (2020) in Kenya demonstrated that experiential concept mapping significantly enhanced both achievement and attitude toward Physics, with no significant gender differences. Similarly, Lestari (2021) in Indonesia reported substantial gains in students' physics problem-solving abilities following experiential STEM-based instruction. Espinoza's (2020) work further emphasized the value of guided inquiry with simulations, particularly for abstract Physics topics such as electricity and waves, underscoring the cognitive advantages of experiential and visualization-rich learning environments.

Gender has increasingly featured as a moderating variable in experiential learning research, though findings remain mixed. Some studies, such as Ngaine (2020) and Obasi and Nwogu (2023), reported no significant gender differences, suggesting that experiential learning is largely gender-inclusive. In contrast, Musa et al. (2021) and Oyeyemi et al. (2021) found significant gender differences in retention, with female students demonstrating superior retention under experiential or simulation-based instruction. Ogbemudia (2023), however, reported higher retention among male students exposed to experiential teaching in Basic Science. These inconsistencies indicate that the moderating role of gender may be context-, subject-, or strategy-specific rather than uniform.

Internationally, gender-focused studies such as Taneja, Kiran, and Bose (2023) in India and Karim, Maries, and Singh (2025) provide nuanced perspectives. While experiential and active-engagement strategies improved outcomes for both males and females, they did not consistently eliminate gender gaps, suggesting that pedagogy alone may be insufficient without broader inclusive practices.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design of pretest, posttest, non-randomized control groups. The target population of this study was 12,036 which was the population of all SS2 Physics students in the FCT. A sample size of 160 students comprising 106 boys and 54 girls drawn from 2 schools within 2 Area Councils out of 6 Area Councils in the FCT were selected using purposive sampling technique. Intact classes in the two (2) senior secondary schools in Kuje Area Council and Abaji Area Council in FCT, Abuja, were used respectively as experimental and control groups. Three instruments used for data collection were Physics Interest Scale Questionnaire (PISQ) which consisted of 20 items, Physics Achievement Test (PAT) which consisted of 30 objective questions, and Physics Retention Test (PRT) which was reshuffled from the PAT. They were validated by experts in the Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja and Government Science and Technical College Abaji, and

reliability values of 0.80 and 0.90 using split halves of PISQ and Pearson product moment correlation coefficients of PAT respectively. The instruments were first administered to the two groups as pretest and later as posttest and retention test respectively. The scores of each student in all the tests were compiled. Data collected were analyzed employing descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and inferential statistics of Mann-Whitney U test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The result is presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One: *What is the difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Experimental and Control Groups on Students' Interest in Physics using Mann-Whitney U test.

Rank of Score			
Group	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Experimental	8605.500	107.56875	38.341878
Control	4274.500	53.43125	36.801705
Total	12880.000	80.50000	46.267441

Mann-Whitney Test

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Experimental	80	107.57	8605.50
Control	80	53.43	4274.50
Mean Difference	160	54.14	

The results in Table 4 show students' PISQ using Experimental Teaching Strategy (ETS) on the experimental group and conventional discussion teaching strategy on the control group with mean scores of 107.57 and 53.43 respectively, with their standard deviation scores of 38.34 and 36.80 respectively. The mean different between the two groups was 54.14 in favour of experimental group. It implies that the use of experiential teaching strategy on the experimental group was more effective in producing a greater effect on the outcome measure compared to the use of the conventional discussion teaching strategy on the control group. That is, the mean interest of students who were taught Physics using experiential teaching strategy was higher than those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy

Research Question Two: *What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?*

Table 5: Mean achievement and Standard Deviation of Posttest Scores of Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Conventional Discussion Teaching Strategy (Control Group).

Group	N	\bar{x}	σ
Experimental	80	22.20	2.98
Control	80	13.98	2.38
Mean difference		8.22	

The results in Table 5 reveal that the post -test mean (\bar{x}) scores of experimental and control groups accordingly were 22.20 and 13.98 with their standard deviation (σ) scores of 2.98 and 2.38 respectively.

The mean difference between the two groups was 8.22 in favour of experimental group. This implies that the students who were taught Physics using experiential teaching strategy in the experimental group gained in achievement more than their conventional discussion teaching strategy counterparts in the control group.

Research Question Three: *What is the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy?*

Table 6: Mean Retention and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Conventional Discussion Teaching Strategy (Control group).

Group	N	\bar{x}	σ
Experimental	80	24.26	3.21
Control	80	12.21	1.76
Mean difference		12.05	

The results in Table 6 reveal that the retention -test mean (\bar{x}) scores of experimental and control groups were 24.26 and 12.21 respectively, with their standard deviation (σ) scores of 3.21 and 1.76 respectively. The mean difference between the two groups was 12.05 in favour of experimental group. This implies that, the experimental group has higher retention rate than the control group. That is, the mean retention of students who were taught Physics using experiential teaching strategy was higher than those taught using conventional discussion teaching strategy.

Research Question Four: *What is the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?*

Table 7: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students' Interest in Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Rank of Score			
Group	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Male	39.52128	47	22.037524
Female	41.89394	33	24.099197
Total	40.50000	80	23.157551

Mann-Whitney Test

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Male	47	39.52	1857.50
Female	33	41.89	1382.50
Mean Difference		-2.37	

The results in Table 7 show male and female response to Physics Interest Scale Questionnaire (PISQ) using Experiential Teaching Strategy (ETS) on the experimental group with mean scores of 39.52 and 41.89 respectively, with their standard deviation scores of 22.04 and 24.09 respectively. The mean difference of both sexes was -2.37. The negative mean difference implies that the value of the outcome in the male group is lower than the value of the outcome in the female group. This difference, though small was in favour of female students indicating that both male and female students have interests in physics, but female have interest slightly higher than their male counterparts when taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy (ETS).

Research Question Five: *What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?*

Table 8: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Physics Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Gender	N	\bar{x}	σ
Male	47	22.79	3.38
Female	33	21.36	2.07
Mean difference		1.43	

The results in Table 8 reveal that the mean (\bar{x}) scores of male and female were 22.79 and 21.36 respectively, with their standard deviation (σ) scores of 3.38 and 2.07 respectively. The mean difference of both gender was 1.43. This difference though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts in Physics using experiential teaching strategy.

Research Question Six: *What is the difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy?*

Table 9: Mean Retention and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Physics Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Gender	N	\bar{x}	σ
Experimental	47	24.68	3.21
Control	33	23.52	3.20
Mean difference		1.16	

The results in Table 9 reveal that the retention-test mean (\bar{x}) scores of male and female were 24.68 and 23.52 respectively, with their standard deviation (σ) scores of 3.21 and 3.20 respectively. The mean difference of both gender was 1.16 in favour of the male students. This indicates that male students' retention capacity is slightly higher than their female counterparts in Physics using experiential teaching strategy.

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.

Table 10: Mann-Whitney U Test Mean Interest Scores of Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy and those taught using Conventional Discussion Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Interest

Source	Score	Decision
Mann-Whitney U	1034.500	
Wilcoxon W	4274.500	
Z	-7.400	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) P-value	.000	Rejected

Mann-Whitney U Test Tests result in Table 10 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean interest scores between Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion teaching strategy in favour of experiential teaching strategy $P(0.0000 < 0.05)$. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that the two teaching strategies differ significantly. However, experiential teaching strategy enhanced students' interest in Physics more than conventional discussion teaching strategy.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.

Table 11: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy and those taught using Conventional Discussion Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Achievement

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected model	27.15.724à	2	1357.862	187.684	0.000	
Intercept	2331.449	1	1331.449	184.033	0.000	
Pretest	17.917	1	17.917	2.477	0.118	
Group	769.672	1	769.672	106.384	0.000	Rejected
Error	1135.870	157	7.235			
Total	56233.000	160				
Corrected Total	3851.594	159				

a.R Squared = .705 (Adjusted R Squared = .701)

ANCOVA Tests result in Table 11 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores between Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion teaching strategy in favour of experiential teaching strategy $F(1,159) = 106.384$, $P(0.0000 < 0.05)$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that experiential teaching strategy is more effective than conventional discussion teaching strategy in achievement of students in Physics.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional discussion teaching strategy.

Table 12: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Retention Scores of Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy and those taught using Conventional Discussion Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Retention

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected model	5800.630à	2	2900.315	432.487	0.000	
Intercept	1857.292	1	1857.292	276.954	0.000	
Pretest	4.574	1	4.574	0.682	0.410	
Group	2241.336	1	2241.336	334.2222	0.000	Rejected
Error	1052.864	157	6.706			
Total	60107.000	160				
Corrected Total	6853.494	159				

a.R Squared = .846 (Adjusted R Squared = .844)

ANCOVA Tests result in Table 12 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores between Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion teaching strategy in favour of experiential teaching strategy $F(1,159) = 334.2222$, $P(0.000 < 0.05)$. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that experiential teaching strategy enhanced students' retention in Physics.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.

Table 13: Mann-Whitney U Test for Mean Interest Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Score	Decision
Mann-Whitney U	729.500	
Wilcoxon W	1857.500	
Z	-.451	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) P-value	.652	Not Rejected

Mann-Whitney U Tests result in Table 13 reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores between male and female Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy $P(0.652 > 0.05)$. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that both male and female Physics students have interest in Physics.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.

Table 14: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type Sum Square	III of df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected model	40.853 ^a	2	20.427	2.376	0.100	
Intercept	1232.525	1	1232.525	143.372	0.000	
Pretest 2	1.562	1	1.562	0.182	0.671	
Gender	40.833	1	40.833	4.750	0.032	Rejected
Error	5.873	77	8.597			
Total	40130.000	80				
Corrected Total	702.800	79				

a. R Squared = .058 (Adjusted R Squared = .034)

ANCOVA Tests result in Table 14 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy $F(1,79) = 4.750$, $P(0.032 < 0.05)$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows significant difference in the achievement of male and female Physics students, in favour of the male students.

Hypothesis Six: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy.

Table 15: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Retention Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physics using Experiential Teaching Strategy.

Dependent Variable: Retention-test

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected model	41.551 ^a	2	20.776	2.017	0.140	
Intercept	1666.299	1	1666.299	161.746	0.000	
Pretest 2	15.206	1	15.206	1.476	0.228	
Gender	32.857	1	32.857	3.189	0.078	Not Rejected
Error	793.249	77	10.302			
Total	47686.000	80				
Corrected Total	834.800	79				

a. R Squared = .050 (Adjusted R Squared = .025)

ANCOVA Tests result in Table 15 reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean retention scores between male and female Physics students who were taught using experiential teaching strategy $F(1,79) = 3.189$, $P(0.078 > 0.05)$. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that experiential teaching strategy enhanced both male and female students' retention in Physics.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that the experiential teaching strategy effectively enhances senior secondary school students' interest, achievement, and retention in Physics. This is justified by multiple studies across diverse educational contexts. For instance, Chawla and Sharma (2021), Obioma, Onyeka, and Okafor-Agbala (2021), and Quaye, Kissi, and Hagan (2025) all reported increased student interest when experiential teaching strategies were applied in Physics, Mathematics, and Tourism, respectively. These studies indicate that hands-on, learner-centred activities and real-life applications stimulate curiosity, motivation, and positive attitudes toward learning, which align with the current study's findings. In terms of achievement, the effectiveness of experiential teaching is reinforced by studies such as Ayomikun and Ogbonna (2019) in Nigeria, Ozden and Gultekin (2019) in Turkey, and Saleh and Subramaniam (2019) in Malaysia, all of which found significantly higher achievement scores among students exposed to experiential strategies compared with those taught using conventional methods. These findings justify the current result, as experiential learning promotes active knowledge construction, practical engagement, and meaningful understanding, which enhance academic performance.

Similarly, for retention, studies by Bada and Akinbobola (2020), Bada and Jita (2021), and Oyeyemi, Olorundare, and Bolaji (2021) confirm that students exposed to experiential strategies retain learned concepts better than those taught traditionally. The alignment between these prior studies and the present findings suggests that repeated engagement, reflection, and collaborative activities inherent in experiential learning strengthen memory and facilitate long-term comprehension.

Regarding gender as a moderating variable, the current findings are largely consistent with previous research. Studies such as Obasi and Nwogu (2023) and Okeke (2019) reported no significant gender differences in interest and retention under experiential learning, supporting the notion that the strategy is largely inclusive and equitable. However, observed gender differences in achievement, with male students performing slightly better, are also corroborated by Nokes-Malach et al. (2018) and Solomon (2019), who attributed such differences to prior exposure, confidence, or differences in how male and female students interact with content. Similarly, Taneja, Kiran, and Bose (2023) found that while experiential learning benefits both genders, its individual components may resonate differently with male and female students.

CONCLUSION

The use of experiential teaching strategy enhanced students' interest, achievement and retention in Physics. No gender disparity existed in the interest and retention capacity of male and female students taught Physics using the experiential teaching strategy. However, there was a gender inequality of male and female students in terms of achievement. This implies that experiential teaching strategy is very rewarding to students in terms of interest and retention capacity regardless of gender, and the use of experiential teaching strategy is capable of bridging the gap in the disparity that existed between male and female students' academic achievement in Physics.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since experiential teaching strategy is found to be an effective strategy which enhanced students' interest in Physics. Physics teachers should accept it in teaching Physics in the senior secondary schools in the FCT and beyond.
2. Physics teachers should discontinue the use of conventional discussion teaching strategy in teaching Physics and embrace the use of experiential teaching strategy because it was found effective in improving students' academic achievement in Physics.
3. Experiential teaching strategy was also found effective in improving Physics students' knowledge retention capacity, therefore Physics teachers should start to use it.
4. The study revealed that both male and female Physics students could be involved in experiential teaching strategy as it was found not to be gender biased.
5. The researcher recommended that Physics teachers should be encouraged to use experiential teaching strategy in teaching Physics as it was found capable to bridge the gap between male and female students' academic achievement in Physics.

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